

A CLINICAL STUDY OF THE ROLE OF CONSTITUTIONAL PRESCRIBING IN CASES OF STRESS INDUCED INSOMNIA IN THE AGE GROUP OF 20-40 YEARS

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ABSTRACT:

Background: The complaint of inadequate sleep, insomnia typically manifests as trouble falling asleep or staying asleep. It's a prevalent sleep disorder. Individuals who suffer from insomnia feel that their sleep quality is inadequate and that this affects their capacity to perform well in social, academic, and occupational contexts. Fatigue, low mood, irritability, malaise, and cognitive impairment are commonly experienced symptoms by the affected individuals. Stress is the result of tension, either physical or emotional. It could stem from anything that makes someone feel angry, frustrated, or anxious. Your body experiences stress in response to a demand or difficulty.

The Insomnia Severity Index (ISI) and the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) can be used to measure an individual's level of insomnia and stress respectively. SATED Questionnaire helps in determining the individual's sleep health. Homoeopathy defines constitution as an individual's structure, composition, physical make-up, or nature, which includes hereditary traits and environmental modifications. In order to bring about a full cure, it is crucial to individualise each case and provide a similitum. The application of a homoeopathic individualised approach in combination with constitutional prescribing will be beneficial for the treatment of sleeplessness brought on by stress.

Methods: This is a non-randomized clinical study on individuals having stress induced insomnia of age group 20 to 40 years from the OPD of Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be) University Homoeopathic Medical College and Research Centre, Khatraj, Pune. Total 32 patients were enrolled out of which 30 patients (male/female) were present till the completion of the study whereas 2 individuals were dropped from the study. The study is done by assessing the scores of Insomnia Severity Index (ISI) and SATED Questionnaire before and after treatment. After detailed case taking individualized constitutional homoeopathic medicine was prescribed.

Result: Total 30 patients (n=30) were selected from the age group of 20 to 40 years, out of which 13 patients were in the age group of 18-24 years, 9 patients were in the age group of 24-30 years, 5 patients were in the age group 30-36 years, 3 patients were above 36 years. The highest percentage of patients belonged to the age group of 18-24 years (43.3%) and the lowest from above 36 years (13.3%). To check the effectiveness of treatment paired t-test was used. The scores before treatment were 18.80 ± 3.76 and after treatment were 8.8 ± 4.63 . T static value is 14.57 and p value (0.000) which is very small.

Conclusion: The results of the study demonstrate the effectiveness of constitutional homoeopathic treatment in treating sleeplessness brought on by stress. Patient's reactions to stress were improved, and their sleep quality was enhanced. With the use of constitutional homoeopathic medicine, the patient's insomnia significantly improved.

Keywords: Stress, Insomnia, Constitutional medicine, Homoeopathy.

INTRODUCTION:

Constitution:

Aristotle was the first person in history to group humans into categories (384–322 BC). He classified persons based on their nature, size, and build in his article "Physiognomy." According to Hippocrates (460–377 BC), each individual has an innate nature that cannot be changed in his "Natura Medicatrix".^[1]

In homoeopathy, constitution refers to a person's unique combination of traits. It deals with underlying miasms, inclinations, and behavioural patterns in addition to the degree of susceptibility. As a result, constitutional remedies function as therapy, prophylaxis, and prevention. The "homoeopathic system

of medicine" is a holistic, all-natural method of treating disease.^[2] The Latin word "CONSTITUERE," which means to build up, establish, or make up, to appoint to give being to, is the source of the English word "CONSTITUTION." Aphorism 5 of the Sixth Edition of the Organon of Medicine places a strong emphasis on the constitution, according to Dr. Hahnemann. Translated to English as "Constitution," Dr. Hahnemann used the term "beschaffenheit" in the German text. The sixth edition of Hahnemann's Organon of Medicine provides an explanation of constitution and is related in aphorisms 5, 102, 117, 138.^[3]

Dr. Von Grauvogl distinguished three categories of constitutional types:

- Carbo-nitrogenoid constitution
- Oxygenoid constitution
- Hydrogenoid constitution

Breathlessness, shortness of breath, quick heartbeat, constipation or diarrhoea, flatulence, and urinary problems are among the general symptoms of the carbo-nitrogenoid constitution, which is marked by inadequate oxygenation. Patients report vertigo, irritability, hypochondria, and gouty swelling among other symptoms.

An oxygenoid constitution, which is also associated with underweightness, is fond of fats and carbohydrates. Patients of this kind respond more favourably to rain or snow than to wind or storms.

It is possible to identify patients with hydrogenoid constitutions using modalities. Living near water or in cold, wet weather makes them feel worse.^[4]

Concepts of Constitution in homoeopathy according to stalwarts:

"That aggregate of hereditary characters, influenced more or less by the environment which determines the individual's reaction, successful or unsuccessful, to the stress of environment," is how STUART CLOSE describes constitution.^[5] "The palpable illness that follows a disturbance in the man's vital power is called physical constitution," according to Dr. KENT.^[6]

Dr. M.L DHAWALE says that everyone has a unique characteristic that gives them their personality, which is partly affected by genes and environmental factors throughout their lives.^[7]

Insomnia:

The complaint of inadequate sleep, insomnia typically manifests as trouble falling asleep or staying asleep. It's a prevalent sleep disorder. Individuals who suffer from insomnia feel that their sleep quality is inadequate and that this affects their capacity to perform well in social, academic, and occupational contexts. Fatigue, low mood, irritability, malaise, and cognitive impairment are commonly experienced symptoms by the affected individuals.^[8]

Stress is the result of tension, either physical or emotional. It might originate from anything that triggers feelings of frustration, rage, or anxiety in someone. Your body experiences stress in response to a demand or difficulty.^[9]

Your body reacts to stress by releasing hormones. Tense muscles, an elevated heart rate, and an alerter brain are all brought on by these chemicals. When you have chronic stress, your body stays alert.^[10] Over time, this puts you at risk for health problems including High Blood Pressure, Diabetes, Obesity and Insomnia.

Symptoms of insomnia:

- Inability to fall asleep or stay asleep in a position that is pleasant
- Awakening in the middle of the night, not being able to fall back asleep, and rising early
- Unable to concentrate on routine chores and having trouble remembering
- Drowsiness, anger, sadness, or anxiety during the day
- Experiencing fatigue or poor energy during the day
- Difficulty focusing
- Excessive irritability, aggressive behaviour, or impatience^[11]

Causes and risk factors:

All age groups are susceptible to insomnia, although the following categories are more likely to have insomnia:^[11]

- Sleep apnea

- Physical exercise
- Asthma
- Pain
- Past mental health conditions, such as depression, etc.
- Stress on an emotional level
- Working shifts that end late at night
- Passing through various time zones
- Having long-term health conditions including diabetes, heart disease, renal disease, lung illness, or Alzheimer's
- Problems related to drug or alcohol usage
- Acid reflux illness of the stomach
- Heavy smoker
- Stress at work

Mechanism:

There are two primary theories about the aetiology of insomnia: cognitive and physiological. According to the cognitive model, rumination and hyperarousal can make it difficult for a person to go asleep and may even cause an episode of insomnia.

The **three** main findings that support the physiological model of insomnia are as follows:

- (1) Elevated levels of catecholamines and cortisol in the urine, which may indicate an increased arousal and HPA axis activity.
- (2) Elevated cerebral glucose utilisation during wakefulness and NREM sleep in insomniacs.
- (3) Elevated heart rate and full body metabolism in insomniacs. When combined, these results point to a disruption of the HPA axis, arousal system, and cognitive system that all contribute to insomnia.^[12]

Diagnosis for stress induced insomnia:

DSM-5 Diagnostic Criteria for Insomnia Disorder	
1. Dissatisfaction with quantity or quality of sleep at least 3 nights a week for at least 3 months , associated with 1 or 2 of the following:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Difficulty falling asleep• Difficulty staying asleep with frequent awakenings or difficulty falling back asleep• Early morning awakenings
2. Causes clinically significant distress or impairment	
3. Occurs even when there is enough time for sleep	
4. Does not occur exclusively during narcolepsy, breathing-related sleeping disorders, circadian rhythm sleep disorders, or a parasomnia	
5. Does not occur exclusively during the course of another mental disorder	
6. Not due to the direct physiologic effects of a substance	

DSM-5 American Psychiatric Association. (2013). Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders. Arlington: American Psychiatric Publishing

 Psychopharmacology Institute

INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

Inclusion criteria:

1. Subjects Should fulfil the diagnostic criteria by DSM-V.
2. Subjects within the range of age group of 20-40 years of both sexes.
3. Subjects fulfilling assessment of stress.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Subjects having Drug induced insomnia and insomnia due to other Neurological causes.
2. Subjects taking conventional treatment for insomnia.
3. Pregnant women and lactating mothers will be excluded.

RESULTS:

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Demographic characteristics of patients

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to age

Age Group	No of patients	Percentage
18-24	13	46.67%
24-30	9	26.67%
30-36	5	13.33%
Above 36	3	13.33%

AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

Figure 1: Pie diagram representing Age-wise distribution of patients

Above table no. 1 and figure 1 show that 43.3% of the patients had an age between 18-24 years, 30% had an age between 24-30 years, and 16.7% of patients had an age between 30-36 and 10% of patients had an age above 36 in the study.

Table 2: Distribution of Patients according to Gender

Gender	Number of patients	Percentage
FEMALE	14	46.67%
MALE	16	53.33%

GENDER WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

Figure 2: Gender-wise distribution of patients

Table no. 2 and Figure 2 show that 53.3% of patients were males and the remaining 46.7% were females in the study.

Table 3: Occupation-wise distribution of patients

Occupation	No of Patients	Percentage
HOME-MAKER	2	6.70%
PROFESSIONALS	10	33.30%
STUDENT	18	60.00%

OCCUPATION WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

Figure 3: Distribution of patients according to Occupation

Table no. 3 and Figure 3 show the Distribution of patients according to their occupation. 60% of patients were Students, and 33.3% of patients were working professionals and 6.7% were homemakers.

Table 4: Remedy-wise distribution of patients.

REMEDY	Number of patients	Percentage
SULPHUR	4	13.33%
ARSENIC ALBUM	3	10.00%
NUX VOMICA	3	10.00%
GRAPHITE	1	3.33%
PULSATILLA	1	3.33%
CALCAREA CARB	3	10.00%
LYCOPODIUM	3	10.00%
SILICEA	1	3.33%
BELLADONNA	1	3.33%
SPONGIA TOSTA	1	3.33%
SEPIA	1	3.33%
RHUS TOX	1	3.33%
CAUSTICUM	1	3.33%
NATRUM MUR	1	3.33%
ACONITE	2	6.67%
LACHESIS	1	3.33%
STAPHYSAGRIA	1	3.33%
KALI CARB	1	3.33%

REMEDY WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

Figure 4: Remedy-wise distribution of patients.

The distribution of patients according to remedies given are shown in Table 5 and Figure 5. Sulphur was given as a remedy to 13.33% of patients followed by Arsenic album which was used for 10% of patients. Aconite was administered to 6.67% of patients, while Pulsatilla was used for the other 3.33% of patients under study.

HYPOTHESIS TESTED:

H₀: Homoeopathic medicines are not effective in the treatment of stress induced insomnia.

Vs

H₁: Homoeopathic medicines are effective in the treatment of stress induced insomnia.

Table 5: Paired t-test and Descriptive statistics of the Score before and after the intervention.

Score	N	Mean \pm SD	T Statistic Value	P-Value
before intervention	30	18.80 \pm 3.76	14.57	0.000**
after intervention	30	8.8 \pm 4.63		
95% CI for mean difference:	(11.5603, 14.2513)			

P Value <0.001, Considered to be statistically highly significant.

Hence there is a significant difference in the **score** before and after the intervention of stress induced insomnia.

A test used: Paired t-test, **: Highly Significant Difference, T Statistic-value: Test Statistic value.

95% CI for mean difference: 95% Confidence Interval for mean difference

MEAN \pm SD OF ISI SCORE BEFORE AND AFTER INTERVENTION

Figure 5: Bar diagram representing the Average \pm SD of ISI score before and after the intervention.

Table 6 and Fig 6 show descriptive Statistics and paired t-test results of the *score* before and after the intervention in the management of stress induced insomnia.

Before treatment, score was 18.80 \pm 3.76 (mean \pm SD) which reduces to 8.8 \pm 4.63 after treatment.

To test the hypothesis of whether the average *score* in patients, before and after the intervention of Homoeopathic medicine remains the same or not, the Paired t-test is used.

T-statistic value is 14.57 with a p-value of 0.000 ** highly significant.

We reject Ho and conclude that there is a significant difference in average *scores* before and after the intervention in the management of stress induced insomnia.

Homoeopathic medicines are effective in the treatment of stress induced insomnia.

Table 6: Descriptive statistics of the SATED Score before and after the intervention.

Score	N	Mean \pm SD
before intervention	30	3.36 \pm 1.21
after intervention	30	8.23 \pm 1.1

MEAN ± SD OF SATED SCORE BEFORE AND AFTER INTERVENTION

Figure 6: Bar diagram representing the Average ± SD of SATED score before and after the intervention.

Table 6 and Fig 6 show descriptive Statistics of the SATED score before and after the intervention in the management of stress induced insomnia.

Before treatment, the score was 3.36 ± 1.21 (mean± SD) which increases to 8.23 ± 1.1 after treatment. We conclude that there is a significant difference in average scores before and after the intervention in the management of stress induced insomnia.

Homoeopathic medicines are effective in improving the sleep health of patients suffering from stress induced insomnia.

Table 7: Distribution Of Patients (%) According To Change In Severity Of Insomnia After Treatment

CHANGE IN SEVERITY OF INSOMNIA AFTER TREATMENT								
SEVERITY	CLINICAL INSOMNIA (SEVERE)		CLINICAL INSOMNIA (MODERATE SEVERITY)		SUBTHRESHOLD INSOMNIA		NO CLINICALLY SIGNIFICANT INSOMNIA	
	COUNT	% OF PATIENTS	COUNT	% OF PATIENTS	COUNT	% OF PATIENTS	COUNT	% OF PATIENTS
BEFORE TREATMENT	7	23.33%	19	63.33%	4	13.33%	0	0%
AFTER TREATMENT	0	0%	4	13.33%	11	36.67%	15	50.00%

DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS (%) ACCORDING TO CHANGE IN SEVERITY OF INSOMNIA AFTER TREATMENT

Figure 7: Distribution Of Patients (%) According To Change In Severity Of Insomnia After Treatment

Table 7 and Figure 7 depicts the change in severity of Insomnia after treatment of patients. Severe Clinical Insomnia before treatment was seen in 23.33% of patients, after treatment it reduced to 0%. Clinical Insomnia with Moderate Severity before treatment was seen in 63.33% of patients, after treatment it reduced to 13.33%. Subthreshold Insomnia before treatment was seen in 13.33% of patients, which increased to 36.67% after treatment depicting the improvement of patients. Patients with No Clinically Significant Insomnia before treatment was 0%, after treatment it increased to 50% depicting the improvement of patients.

Table 8: Distribution of patients according to improvement after intervention.

Improvement	Number of patients	Percentage
MARKED	15	50.00%
MILD	4	13.33%
MODERATE	11	36.67%

IMPROVEMENT WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

Figure 8: Distribution of patients according to the improvement after intervention.

Table 8 and Figure 8 show the distribution of patients according to improvement after intervention for stress induced insomnia. 50% of patients had marked improvement after treatment, 36.7% of the patients showed moderate level of improvement whereas 13.3% showed mild improvement after treatment of stress induced insomnia.

SUMMARY:

In this non-randomized single blind clinical study 30 cases of stress induced insomnia in the age group of 20 to 40 years from both the sexes which were not on any other treatment during 5 follow ups were treated at OPD of **BHARATI VIDYAPEETH HOMOEOPATHIC HOSPITAL**, peripheral OPD and various camps organised by **BHARATI MEDICAL FOUNDATION** both in Rural and Urban areas. After proper and detailed case taking well selected constitutional medicine was prescribed on the basis of their individual constitutions. The remedy was administered either in 30, 200 or 1M potency according to the requirement of the case. Follow ups were taken at interval of 15 days. After analysis of data collected at the completion of the study suggests marked improvement in 50% of the patients. Change in severity of Insomnia after treatment of patients were noted as, Severe Clinical Insomnia before treatment was seen in 23.33% of patients, after treatment it reduced to 0%. Clinical Insomnia with Moderate Severity before treatment was seen in 63.33% of patients, after treatment it reduced to 13.33%. Subthreshold Insomnia before treatment was seen in 13.33% of patients, which increased to 36.67% after treatment depicting the improvement of patients. Patients with No Clinically Significant Insomnia before treatment was 0%, after treatment it increased to 50% depicting the improvement of patients. So, the study indicates that the role of Homoeopathic constitutional medicine in the cases of stress induced insomnia is significant and useful.

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